

A Diagram of Intermittent Habitability for Eccentric Exoplanets

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Abstract

I introduce a simple diagram that combines semi-major axis, eccentricity, and stellar properties to quantify the fraction of orbital period spent within habitable zone. The diagram identifies whether an orbit lies fully within, fully outside, or partly overlaps the habitable zone. The diagram reveals that exoplanets sometimes classified as outside the HZ actually spend more than half of their orbit within it. Climate modeling further suggests that planetary systems may retain habitable conditions even outside formal HZ boundaries. These cases should be considered when selecting targets for biosignature searches.

1 introduction

Generally, a planet is considered to be located within the habitable zone (HZ) when its distance from the parent star lies within the boundaries where water can exist in liquid form. These boundaries can be readily derived from the star's effective temperature, according to formulas given by [Kopparapu et al. \(2013, 2014\)](#).

Contemporary research shows that habitability could extend to planets whose orbits are only partially included in the HZ due to their eccentricity. Some studies suggest that orbital eccentricity can, under certain conditions, improve surface habitability.

[Liu et al. \(2024\)](#) demonstrated that a high orbital eccentricity ($e=0.4$) outside the classical habitable zone can, under certain conditions, enlarge the habitable surface area by about +25% for more than 80% of the orbit compared to a circular trajectory. The authors use an Earth-twin configuration with zero obliquity and a fixed mean insolation (to enable straightforward comparison), and they account for surface temperature, the hydrological cycle, albedo, radiative forcings, and atmospheric circulation. Their work suggests that under certain modeled conditions, orbital eccentricity is likely to expand habitability relative to circular analogs. This implies that the classical habitable zone, defined for circular orbits, may need to be revised to include eccentric orbits.

[Jernigan et al. \(2023\)](#) showed that although stellar flux decreases with distance from the host star, climate models suggest that increasing eccentricity from 0 to 0.2 leads to a rise of about 5 °C in the annual average surface air temperature, and that a further increase from 0.2 to 0.4 results in an additional 13 °C warming. They concluded that increasing orbital eccentricity in planets that harbor oceans also implies an increase in biological productivity in the case of marine life, and thus a stronger expression of atmospheric biosignatures. They stated that highly eccentric planets would therefore be excellent candidates in the search for biosignatures.

[Rodríguez-Mozos and Moya \(2025\)](#) take orbital eccentricity into account in the construction of their *Statistical-likelihood Exoplanetary Habitability Index* (SEPHI 2.0). Their approach converts the eccentric orbit into an equivalent circular radius ([2017](#)), thus relying on the principle of an average or equivalent flux. The overall probability of habitability (SEPHI 2.0) is therefore based on normalizing the orbit to an equivalent flux and remains, in a sense, blind to the fractional and intermittent nature of orbital residence within the HZ. This approach could be enriched by considering the temporal dynamics of eccentric orbits intermittently crossing the HZ.

In light of these studies, I propose to design a diagram that facilitates the visualization of the fraction of the orbital period spent within the boundaries of habitable zone.

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2 Intermittent habitability diagram

I adopt a stellar-independent framework, such that the representation does not presuppose a particular spectral type of the host star.

2.1 stellar-independent x-axis

To compare orbits around different host stars on a common horizontal scale, I map the orbital size a to a unit-habitable-zone (HZ) coordinate

$$\alpha = \frac{\ln a - \ln d_{\text{in}}}{\ln R}, \quad R \equiv \frac{d_{\text{out}}}{d_{\text{in}}},$$

so that the conservative HZ interval $[d_{\text{in}}, d_{\text{out}}]$ *always* corresponds to $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, irrespective of the stellar luminosity and temperature or absolute HZ size. The inner and outer HZ distances are

$$d_{\text{in}} = \sqrt{\frac{L_{\star}}{S_{\text{eff,in}}(T_{\text{eff}})}}, \quad d_{\text{out}} = \sqrt{\frac{L_{\star}}{S_{\text{eff,out}}(T_{\text{eff}})}},$$

with $S_{\text{eff}}(T_{\text{eff}})$ given by the polynomials for the moist-greenhouse (inner) and maximum-greenhouse (outer) limits (Kopparapu et al., 2013, 2014). In the ratio

$$R = \frac{d_{\text{out}}}{d_{\text{in}}} = \sqrt{\frac{S_{\text{eff,in}}(T_{\text{eff}})}{S_{\text{eff,out}}(T_{\text{eff}})}},$$

the stellar luminosity L_{\star} cancels, leaving only a dependence on T_{eff} . Using logarithms makes the transformation *scale-invariant* and appropriate for a multiplicative interval: the incident flux scales as $F \propto a^{-2}$, so equal *ratios* in a (i.e., equal differences in $\ln a$) correspond to equal multiplicative changes in flux.

With this choice, a circular orbit lies inside the HZ if $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. For an eccentric orbit (plotted with eccentricity e on the y -axis), periastron and apastron map to

$$\alpha_{\text{peri}} = \frac{\ln(a(1-e)) - \ln d_{\text{in}}}{\ln R}, \quad \alpha_{\text{apo}} = \frac{\ln(a(1+e)) - \ln d_{\text{in}}}{\ln R},$$

so one can read directly whether the orbit *stays within*, *crosses*, or *lies outside* the HZ in a host-independent way.

2.2 Habitable fraction of the orbital period

The fraction of the orbital period that a planet spends within the habitable zone can be obtained by combining the geometry of the ellipse with Kepler's second law. The orbital radius is expressed as a function of the true anomaly, $r(\nu) = \frac{a(1-e^2)}{1+e\cos\nu}$. Kepler's law of areas implies that the time element associated with an increment of true anomaly is weighted as $dt \propto (1+e\cos\nu)^{-2} d\nu$.

Thus, the fraction of the orbital period spent inside the habitable zone is given by

$$f_{\text{HZ}}(a, e) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\nu_A}^{\nu_B} \frac{(1-e^2)^{3/2}}{(1+e\cos\nu)^2} d\nu,$$

where ν_A and ν_B are the true anomalies corresponding to the inner and outer HZ boundaries. The diagram shows isolines corresponding to orbits for which 0%, 50%, 75% or 100% of the orbital period is spent within the HZ.

The diagram displays 75% isolines that are defined in the (α, e) plane (for fixed $R = d_{\text{out}}/d_{\text{in}}$) as the loci where an eccentric orbit spends exactly 75% of its period inside the habitable zone. For each (α, e) , we locate the true anomalies at which the Keplerian radius $r(\nu)$ intersects the HZ boundaries ($r = 1$ and $r = R$), then convert these angles to mean anomalies via Kepler's equation to obtain the time fraction f . The 75% contour is the level set $f(\alpha, e; R) = 0.75$, i.e. the locus of points (α, e) satisfying

this condition without an explicit closed-form relation between α and e ; it is computed numerically. Trivial cases are handled explicitly: $f = 1$ when the entire orbit lies within the HZ, and $f = 0$ when it never enters.

Figure 1: Atlas of intermittent habitability diagrams: fraction of orbital period within the conservative HZ as a function of eccentricity and stellar T_{eff}

3 conclusion

The diagram of intermittent habitability presented here provides a practical and heuristic tool for rapidly assessing the orbital habitability of eccentric exoplanets. By combining semi-major axis and eccentricity with stellar properties, it allows one to distinguish at a glance between planets that are always, never, or intermittently within the habitable zone. This approach highlights cases where more than 75% of the orbit is spent in habitable conditions, suggesting that climate buffering may extend habitability even during the remaining phases outside the HZ. The diagram can help avoid discarding planets with significant habitable phases and aid in target selection.

I have chosen to adopt the conservative habitable zone boundaries, but the diagram could also be presented in a more optimistic form by using the Recent-Venus and Early-Mars limits.

My proposed diagram complements the catalog-based empirical approach of [Bohl et al. \(2025\)](#) who computed the fraction of orbital period spent within the habitable zone for known rocky exoplanets. While their work provides an essential database and statistical overview, the diagram presented here offers a complementary visual tool, grounded in formal orbital geometry, to interpret how eccentricity shapes intermittent habitability. The combination of formalism and empirical data is particularly valuable: empirical catalogues allow us to assess habitability fractions across the observed exoplanet population, whereas a formal diagram highlights the underlying dynamical structure that governs these fractions. It seems important to develop habitability-fraction diagrams both from theoretical models and from observational data, thereby providing a heuristic framework for rapidly identifying promising targets in the search for biosignatures.

It is nevertheless important to distinguish between planets whose fraction of orbital period outside

the HZ lies interior to the inner edge and those whose fraction lies exterior to the outer edge. Excursions inside the inner edge are likely to be more damaging for long-term habitability, as intense irradiation may trigger runaway greenhouse processes and water loss. By contrast, excursions beyond the outer boundary (typically on the right-hand side of the diagram) may, under favorable circumstances, be mitigated by climatic inertia: the thermal capacity of oceans and atmospheres can buffer short periods of reduced stellar flux. However, this buffering is not guaranteed; it depends on the depth and duration of the excursion as well as on planetary properties such as atmospheric composition and heat storage capacity.

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